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IMMUNOLOGICAL PREDICTORS OF COMPLICATIONS AFTER TRANSPEDICULAR FIXATION IN PATIENTS WITH SPONDYLOLISTHESIS

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Despite advances in transpedicular spinal fixation (TPSF) technologies, the incidence of postoperative complications in spondylolisthesis remains high, especially in patients with immune imbalance. Identification of immunological predictors of complications may facilitate a personalized approach to prevention. It has been established that local and systemic inflammation in response to implantation is mediated by the activation of innate immune cells—neutrophils, macrophages, and dendritic cells—accompanied by the secretion of proinflammatory cytokines. This can lead to impaired bone tissue repair. Dysfunction of regulatory T cells and an imbalance between the Th1/Th2/Th17 profile are accompanied by a decrease in antigen-specific tolerance and an increase in autoimmune reactions. Matrix metalloproteinases, expressed in response to surgical trauma, promote the degradation of the intercellular matrix and impede implant integration into bone tissue. Several studies describe the role of Toll-like receptors and activation of NF- κ B signaling pathways in the induction of chronic inflammation around implants.

Objective: To develop a risk stratification model based on immunological parameters in patients with spondylolisthesis who underwent TPP.

Materials and Methods: A total of 146 individuals were examined, including 126 patients with spondylolisthesis and 20 clinically healthy controls. A model for assessing immune risk was developed based on CD4+, CD16+/56+, IL-6, TNF- α , MMP-9, NLR, and IgA. Low- and high-risk groups were identified.

Results: A high risk of complications was found to be associated with severe CD4+ deficiency, hyperproduction of cytokines (IL-6, TNF- α), increased MMP-9 activity, and high NLR levels. These parameters formed the basis of the prognostic scale.

Conclusion: Immunological stratification allows for the timely identification of patients with a high risk of complications and the development of individualized treatment strategies, including targeted immunoprophylaxis.

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CERTIFICATE

SAFAROV JASUR TEMIROVICH

was awarded for his active participation in the scientific work on the topic

***“Immunological Predictors of Complications After
Transpedicular Fixation in Patients With
Spondylolisthesis”***

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